

Heterobeltiosis for important yield-attributing traits in wild-abortive CMS-bred basmati rice

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Global rice production must reach 800 million t from the current production of 645 million t to meet world food demand by 2025. Of the many approaches to raise the yield ceiling, exploitation of hybrid vigor (heterosis) holds much promise. Expansion of leaf area, attributed to an increase in number of tillers, is found to be a major factor in achieving heterosis in hybrid rice during a 30-d period after transplanting. Though the degree of heterosis decreases thereafter, it increases again after heading, contributing to higher grain yield (Kabaki 1993).

An experiment was conducted at the SKUAST main campus in Jammu, India (32°14'N latitude, 74°50'E longitude, altitude of 356 m asl, av annual rainfall of 1,166 mm), during the wet season of 2005-06. The soil was an Alfisol, with pH 7.2. The basic experimental material comprised three wild-abortive (WA) cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile (CMS) lines in a basmati background – Pusa 3A, Pusa 5A, and Pusa 6A. These were crossed with seven elite restorer lines – HUR-FG-78, HUR-FG-79, HUR-FG-81, HUBR-2-11, HUR-BL-135-AR, HUR-BL-137-AR, and RR 564. Eleven effective crosses were selected for this study and planted along with their parental lines for evaluation in a compact family block design with three replications under irrigated conditions. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 2-m-long single rows for both parental lines and F1 progeny (a single seedling per hill at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm).

The physiological efficiency of rice hybrids depends on net assimilation rate (NAR) – the mean rate of dry matter production per unit leaf area. This is measured by the equation $((W2 - W1) (\text{Loge } A2 - \text{Loge } A1) / (t2 - t1) (A2 - A1))$, where W1 and W2 and A1 and A2 are plant dry weights and leaf areas at times t1 and t2, respectively, and expressed as mg dm⁻² d⁻¹ (is this the mg of dry matter squared? per day?). In our study, most of the hybrids showed both positive and negative heterosis in NAR recorded for successive growth periods. All hybrids exhibited significant heterosis with respect to NAR, ranging from 20.96% positive heterosis in Pusa 3A/HUR-FG-79 to 3.05% in Pusa 6A/HUR-BL-135-AR from seedling to tillering (Table 1). Likewise, from tillering to flowering, hybrids showed significant heterosis (from -83.88% in Pusa 5A/RR 564 to

52.60% in Pusa 6A/RR 564). All hybrids had similar heterosis patterns from flowering to maturity and during the whole growth period.

Leaf area index (LAI) is one of the key physiological determinants of biological yield. Most of the hybrids analyzed in this study revealed significant heterosis for LAI at tillering, flowering, and maturity stages. Heterosis at tillering ranged from -40.86% in Pusa 5A/RR 564 to 87.46% in Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-81. At flowering, a similar trend was observed, with heterosis ranging from -36.51% in Pusa 5A/RR 564 to 87.34% in Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-81. However, at maturity, eight hybrids revealed significant positive heterosis (ranging from 14.61% in Pusa 6A/HUR-BL-137-AR to 299.04% in Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-78). The increased yield has been attributed to the higher dry matter because of the higher LAI and crop growth rate (CGR). The increased harvest index is due to the increase in spikelet number and, to some extent, increase in grain weight (Akita et al 1986, Blanco et al 1986, Agata 1990). Higher NARs were observed from seedling to tillering stages in most hybrids; these subsequently declined during later crop growth stages (Tables 1-3).

The parental lines had the highest LAI at flowering, but it decreased toward maturity (data not shown). This trend in mean performance with respect to physiological characters has also been noted in hybrids. Three promising hybrids were identified to have the highest level of desired heterosis for grain yield—Pusa 3A/RR 564, Pusa 3A/HUR-FG-79, and Pusa 6A/RR 564. Most of these hybrids outperformed the parental lines in terms of CGR, relative growth rate, and LAI. Using parents with high physiological efficiency will thus ensure that positive heterosis is achieved in hybrids.

References

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Table 1. Estimates (%) of net assimilation rate (NAR) and leaf area index (LAI) of basmati rice hybrids as indicators of heterobeltiosis.

Genotype	NAR				LAI		
	Seedling to tillering	Tillering to flowering	Flowering to maturity	Whole growth duration	Tillering	Flowering	Maturity
Pusa 6A/RR 564	-53.15**	52.60**	6.10**	27.39**	-12.33**	-9.95*	19.95**
Pusa 3A/RR 564	-70.12**	15.56**	-53.84**	-7.73**	17.94**	21.02**	36.81**
Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-81	-32.69**	-66.85**	-23.6**	-11.61**	87.4**	87.34**	80.36**
Pusa 3A/HUR-FG-78	-22.04**	-45.77**	-19.89**	-18.68**	25.40**	28.92**	45.96**
Pusa 3A/HUR-FG-79	20.96**	-39.26**	-23.82**	12.06**	-6.42*	-1.84	0.87
Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-78	-48.58**	-68.95**	-69.9**	-32.64**	59.44**	58.27**	299.4**
Pusa 5A/HUBR-2-11	-29.84**	-9.11**	3.05	-0.70	-4.74	-5.97*	1.07
Pusa 6A/HUR-BL-137-AR	-13.76**	48.42**	11.33**	9.71**	-35.73**	-42.32**	14.61**
Pusa 6A/HUR-BL-135-AR	3.05**	-36.12**	9.08**	31.75**	-10.42*	-11.74**	0.00
Pusa 6A/HUR-FG-78	-40.68**	-61.56**	-38.07**	-35.84**	26.71**	32.68**	203.95**
Pusa 5A/RR-564	-64.50**	-83.88**	-58.07**	-37.59**	-40.86**	-36.51**	-30.32**
SE	1.36	0.52	0.69	0.77	0.18	0.35	0.22
CD (0.05)	2.84	1.10	1.45	1.61	0.38	0.69	0.45

*/** = significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Table 2. Heterobeltiosis estimates (%) for grain yield and its attributes in basmati rice hybrids.

Genotype	Tillers plant ⁻¹	Effective tillers plant ⁻¹	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹	Grain yield
Pusa 6A/RR 564	19.58	23.92**	59.34	20.81**
Pusa 3A/RR 564	10.69	19.88**	70.70**	23.75**
Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-81	78.66**	75.10**	112.35**	11.93**
Pusa 3A/HUR-FG-78	-8.1	-1.21	142.13**	8.91**
Pusa 3A/HUR-FG-79	-9.36	31.88**	73.84**	22.08**
Pusa 5A/HUR-FG-78	27.26*	27.76**	147.00**	18.00**
Pusa 5A/HUBR-2-11	36.34**	28.82**	100.69**	3.24
Pusa 6A/HUR -137-AR	93.92**	87.58**	0.34	-28.26**
Pusa 6A/HUR -135-AR	102.43**	147.52**	21.42	-41.91**
Pusa 6A/HUR-FG-78	46.47*	43.13**	84.00**	-0.56
Pusa 5A/RR 564	2.38	1.76	38.63	-12.59**
SE	3.14	1.14	27.70	0.44
CD (0.05)	6.57	2.39	57.78	0.93

*/** = significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Table 3. Mean performance indicators of parental lines showing the highest heterobeltiosis in basmati rice hybrids.

Yield-attributing trait	Pusa 3A	Pusa 5A	RR 564	HUR-FG-78	HUR-FG-79
Morphological					
Total tillers per plant	20.53	18.03	14.45	13.36	17.16
Effective tillers per plant	18.05	17.00	12.93	12.43	15.83
Spikelets per panicle	88.67	112.00	132.00	125.00	122.33
Physiological					
Net assimilation rate ^a					
Seedling to tillering	75.14	122.24	188.14	127.52	110.11
Tillering to flowering	19.66	46.74	7.70	7.13	10.04
Flowering to maturity	26.19	40.21	12.51	15.06	24.84
Whole duration	44.09	56.58	43.84	53.09	42.41
Leaf area index					
Tillering	5.91	2.89	6.24	6.14	4.85
Flowering	6.50	3.27	7.23	7.19	5.40
Maturity	4.59	2.10	4.06	2.35	3.02

^aMeasured in mg dm⁻² d⁻¹.